

Analyzing Quality of Educational Practices and Students' Social-Emotional Learning in Public Elementary Schools

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Abstract

This study explores the effect of Quality Education Practices (QEP) on the emotional Learning (SEL) of students in public elementary schools in the province of Punjab, Pakistan. The objectives were to i) find out the QEP in public elementary schools, ii) explore the students' SEL level, and iii) examine the relationship of QEP with students' SEL. Major research questions were: i) what are the practices for quality education in public elementary schools? What is the level of SEL of students in public elementary schools? Is there any relationship between QEP and students' SEL? The study was descriptive, and the design was correlational. A total of 200 headteachers, 1688 teachers and 4011 students of the 8th class were selected through a multistage random sampling technique. Six self-developed five-point rating scales were used. To get the opinion from respondents. A major conclusion was that most public elementary schools in Punjab have high levels of overall QEP and SEL. A strong positive relationship was found between overall QEP and overall SEL of students, and QEP strongly predicts the SEL of students. It was recommended that the Directorate of Staff Development of Punjab introduce training programs for teachers to comprehend and improve the SEL of students.

Key Words

Quality Education Practices, Social Emotional Learning, Elementary Level Students

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Introduction

Education is considered a process and a powerful activity that brings desirable change to a nation's social and cultural life (Hussain, 2004; Bibi, 2011). Further, quality in education is the pathway for considerable progress, economic growth, and holistic development of society, organization, or country (Malik, 2017). For the overall development of society, quality education plays a key role through educational institutions (Malik, 2017). School is the basic formal institution where society sends their children to learn and start the developmental process; this process depends upon the quality of their learning. Quality education practices confirm the excellence in education and provide lifelong learning to students.

There are two principles of quality of education: one is the cognitive development of students, and the second is the role of education in endorsing the standards and manners for students in the whole development of students. The concept of Quality education helps in understanding the multidimensional role of education as political,

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cultural, and economic dimensions of quality education are interdependent (OECD, [2018](#)). Practices, processes, or standards for quality education practices are the inputs (combination of resources), processes (teachers, pedagogy, textbooks, and learning materials that support the acquisition of knowledge and other higher-order skills), and outcomes (knowledge, skills, and attitudes that foster positive participation in society (Ministry of Federal Education and Professional Training of Pakistan, 2016; Salam, [2015](#)). For quality education practices, as in other provinces of Pakistan, the Punjab government also took different initiatives. These initiatives address the needs and meetings, as well as the gaps in quality education and its delivery mechanism (Malik, [2017](#)). The vision of the government of Punjab, Pakistan, is to enable every child to acquire creativity, which is possible through dedicated classroom teaching. Every student should be able to reveal and comprehend knowledge in basic skills, develop increased higher-order thinking, and develop a strong wisdom of identity and citizenship at the end of elementary school education (New Deal 2018-2023. [2018](#); Bruno & Garcia-Varela, [2023](#)).

To ensure quality education practices in schools, the government of Punjab launched the School Reform Road Map (SRRM) in April 2010. In this program, different indicators were established to achieve the target of quality education, i.e. Students' enrollment, attendance, and retention of students' academic performance, ensuring 100% teachers' presence, provision of different missing facilities, improvement in the infrastructure, reduction of the problems of overcrowding and multi-grade classrooms and teachers etc. (DSD, [2014](#)). The latest reforms of school education in Punjab for quality education practices are transformation in teacher effectiveness, strengthening basic competencies of students, reforms in middle-level education (post-primary) through restructuring curriculum and reshaping assessment, strengthening school education department, and empowering the school leaders and administrators (New Deal 2018-2023. [2018](#)). Quality education practices improve, enhance, and ensure quality education that is based on cognitive and noncognitive skills (New Deal 2018-2023. [2018](#); Lipnevich, Bergold, & Preckel, [2022](#)). Cognitive and noncognitive skills are essential for lifelong learning as well as the whole development of students, helpful for student's readiness for learning, flourishing in school, livelihood, and life, such as development attitude (Sá & Serpa, [2020](#)). The new emerging trend in education is Social Emotional Learning. The skills, feelings, attitudes and mindsets that support students towards better careers, along with growing mindset, courage, and sense of possession in school (Matson, [2017](#)). Educationists use many names for SEL, such as soft skills, 21st-century skills, noncognitive skills, character building, and whole child development (Gehlbach, [2015](#)).

Social-Emotional Learning (SEL) is helpful to students for their academic success (Kuo, Casillas, & Allen, [2019](#)). SEL is an important component of learning for students that determines several benefits for them. It increases the academic achievements of students and supports students in developing restored, better-off people and active citizens (Bar-On, [2005](#); Cohen, [2006](#)). SEL contributes to the children's ability to identify and realize emotions, figure out associations, resolve interpersonal conflicts, and make moral judgments (Payton et al., [2000](#)).

Review of Related Literature

Quality is the attribute of creating a good or service without flaws (Anderson, [2006](#)). According to the industrial explanation, service is attained when requirements are satisfied, and quality is an essential, quantifiable component of industrial goods. (Baird, [2006](#)). The contextual mode, or the flexible operational framework in which the school operates, may be used for the educational quality of input, process, and output. The physical resources, human resources, administrators, instructors, and other personnel are called input, instructional procedure, the method provided by the setting in which the school operates (the method through which the national curriculum is carried out) are referred to as process, and student learning and academic achievements are referred as output (Haider, [2008](#); Ministry of Federal Education and Professional Training, 2016). Arjomandi, Kestell, & Grimshaw ([2009](#)) define quality as having goals for a particular method or technique in a particular scenario at a particular moment.

Quality Assurance

Meeting and beyond customer expectations, everyone's work, continuous improvement, recognition, and reward. Leadership, collaboration, assessment, and methodical problem-solving are characteristics of quality (Gibbs, [2010](#); Flores-Molina, [2011](#)). The process by which organizations carry out their duties by combining the administrative perspective with the measures taken to guarantee that each individual involved in the activity is held accountable is known as quality assurance (Bayraktar, Tatoglu & Zaim, [2008](#)). As quality is the satisfaction of clients, some positive steps like administration, management, teaching methodologies, proper assessment and evaluation, access, equality, facilities, qualification of teachers, co-curricular activities, and technologies are the keys to gaining success in quality education. Furthermore, the strategic and proper method of teaching enhances the quality of education (Darling-Hammond, [2015](#)). In any educational institution, quality of education is provided based on many factors, like a good learning environment, teachers, teaching methods, and teaching system (Hattie, [2018](#)). The mechanism of quality assurance enables the process and product (Bayraktar, Tatoglu & Zaim, [2008](#)). Quality assurance is a method to evaluate the proficiency of processes and arrangements required to achieve the objectives of an organization or system. Quality assurance denotes the processes and actions that assess the input process and output (Reid, [2011](#)).

Social Emotional Learning

The Social Emotional Learning (SEL) is a process through which students acquire the abilities, knowledge and attitude essential toward realising and regulating emotions, creating and coming across optimistic goals, showing empathy for fellows, establishing constructive relations, and making good decisions (Collaborative for Academic, Social, and Emotional Learning (CASEL), [2015](#)). The capacity to comprehend, control, and communicate the social and emotional sides of the life of a person that facilitates the effective completion of responsibilities is known as social-emotional competence (CASEL, [2015](#)).

Over the past two decades, there has been some shift in the definition of SEL as five interrelated competencies are included such as (i) Self-Awareness competency, which is said to involve being cognizant of one's feelings and those of others; (ii) Self-Management competency, which is involve regulating one's emotion and the learning process; (iii) Social Awareness competency which is seen to incorporate the ability of understanding and interpreting the sentiment and attitude of others and (iv) Interpersonal relationships, or relationship skills competency that enables a person to maintain, manage, and work out share relationships and suffer conflicts in stable and healthy ways. (v) Responsible decision-making competency that is about identifying issues in any sphere of life and finding ways to solve these problems in a morally and ethically correct manner (Shanker, 2015; CASEL, [2015](#), 2017, & 2019). According to CASEL ([2015](#)), SEL is a process of helping individuals' social-emotional capacities for learning, development, or functioning at various ages. In this way, people acquire a structure in cognition, emotion, and behaviour to smooth function in school and other aspects of life (Gueldner, Feuerborn & Merrell, [2020](#)). On the other hand, the strength of the CASEL definition emphasizes the fact that SEL is a process of building competencies in children and adults about academic success and in life in general. Despite the worldwide importance of social-emotional competencies, experience and display of feelings are knowledgeable. The definition of CASEL is consequential to social and emotional capability and doesn't consider multicultural diversity in emotions (Humphrey, [2013](#)).

Role of School in Social-Emotional Learning

Schools play a pivotal character in the cognitive development of students, but educational institutions should develop social-emotional skills among students (Corcoran, 2017). Emotional competencies help students to increase knowledge and develop basic skills, enhanced social behaviour and self-esteem, sympathetic learning

environments, and better attitudes about self, others, and the school; these core skills help reduce behaviour-related problems, reduce emotional stress, specially improved academic performance of the students in the classroom (CASEL, 2015).

The powerful contribution of school is the academic and social-emotional facets of teaching and student learning (Corcoran & Tormey, 2012; Corcoran & O'Flaherty, 2017; Corcoran, 2018). SEL helps students to make social relationships with others and learn in an active way, which enhances their achievements in school and practical life (Nind, 2011; Clarke et al., 2015; Weare & Yoshikawa et al., 2015).

Statement of the Problem

Quality of education has become a worldwide agenda at all educational levels; the quality of basic education is significant not only for preparing students for the forthcoming educational levels but also for preparing them with compulsory life skills (DeJaeghere & Murphy-Graham, 2022). Findings of different studies indicated the great significance of social-emotional knowledge for lifelong learning and academic achievements of students. (Zins, Bloodworth, Weissberg, & Walberg, 2007; Durlak, Weissberg, Dymnicki, Taylor, Schellinger, 2011; Kuo, Casillas & Allen, 2019). For the overall development of students and society, quality education plays a key role in educational institutions (Malik, 2017). Quality education practices have been designed in Pakistan to warrant free and necessary education for all and lifelong learning of students (Parveen & Tran, 2020). Punjab, the largest province of Pakistan, has taken many modern reforms in education and initiatives for quality education; these initiatives not only ensure the facilities in schools, access, and opportunity but also promote lifelong learning of students. Meanwhile, quality education claims lifelong learning as it has a strong relationship with the achievements of students and also plays a central role in the academic success and happiness of students (Bar-On, 2005; Cohen, 2006; Kuo, Casillas, & Allen, 2019). Hence, the present research has been designed to study the quality education practices and social-emotional learning of students in Public elementary schools in Punjab.

Research Objectives

The following were the objectives of the study:

1. To find out the Quality Education Practices in public elementary schools
2. To explore the students' Social Emotional Learning level in public elementary schools.
3. To examine the relationship of Quality Education Practices with students' Social Emotional Learning in public elementary schools.

Research Questions

1. What is the level of Quality Education Practices in male and female public elementary schools?
2. What is the level of students' Social Emotional Learning in male and female public elementary schools?
3. Is there any relationship between overall quality education practices and students' Social Emotional Learning?

Methodology

The study was descriptive in nature, with a correlational design utilising a survey technique to collect the data. The study examined the relationship between quality education practices and social-emotional learning of students in public elementary schools in Punjab, Pakistan. So, there were three types of population: all headteachers, all teachers, and all students of public elementary schools situated in the Punjab province of Pakistan.

The multistage random sampling technique was used to select a representative sample. In 1st stage, the province of Punjab is administratively divided into nine divisions. In 2nd stage, 10 districts were randomly selected on an equal proportion basis from the selected division, two districts from each selected division; in 3rd stage, 20 tehsils (two tehsils, one urban and one rural from each selected district) were randomly selected on equal proportion bases from 10 selected districts, in the 4th stage, 20 schools (10 male and 10 female) were randomly chosen from each selected tehsil, and in 5th stage, all headteacher, all teachers and all students of 8th class were taken from each selected school.

Six self-developed five-point rating scale bilingual (English and Urdu) instruments were administered to find out the quality of education practices in schools and the social-emotional learning of students. Each scale was prepared separately for headteachers, teachers, and students. The nature of items and responses were the same, but the numbers of items were different according to their nature and relevancy to respondents. Scales were validated through expert opinion, and reliability was established using Cronbach's Alpha and factors analysis. Cronbach's Alpha values of QEP scales of headteachers, teachers, and students were 0.92, 0.88 and 0.75, respectively, and Cronbach's alpha values of SEL scales of headteachers, teachers, and students were 0.95, 0.94, and 0.83 respectively.

Due to the scattered sample and short time, the information was sought from headteachers, teachers, and students of 8th grade studying in public elementary schools in Punjab personally and with the help of four trained research assistants through the survey method. Instructions were printed out on every scale for every respondent. Frequency, percentage, mean score, t-test and ANOVA were applied through the SPSS-23 version to analyze the data.

Data Analysis & Results

Table 1

Levels of Quality Education Practices

Variable	Status of Respondents	Levels						Mean score
		Low		Average		High		
		%	F	%	F	%	F	
Quality Education Practices	Headteachers	0%	0/200	32.5%	65/200	67.5%	135/200	2.68
	Teachers	0%	0/1688	23%	387/1688	77%	1301/1688	2.78
	Students	0%	0/4011	05%	180/4011	95%	3831/4011	2.96

Table 1 reflects the levels of quality education practices. The 67.5% of headteachers (135/200) with a mean score of 2.68 reported a high level of overall quality education practices in public elementary schools of Punjab, while 32.5% (65/200) reported an average level. The majority (77%) of teachers (1301/1688) with a mean score of 2.78 reported a high level of overall quality education practices in public elementary schools of Punjab. Most (95%) of the students (3831/4011), with a mean score of 2.96, showed that overall quality education practices in public elementary schools in Punjab were of a high level.

Table 2

Comparison of Headteachers' Teachers' and Students' Views about QEP

Dependent variables		Some of the squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig. (p.value)
QEP	Between Groups	1574124.681	2	787062.340	6319.810	.000
	Within Groups	734281.482	5896	124.539		
	Total	2308406.163	5898			

p<0.05

Table 2 reflects the comparison of views of headteachers, teachers, and students from public elementary schools in Punjab about quality education practices. The F value 6319.810 and p-value $0.000 < 0.05$ indicate a significant difference among the views of headteachers, teachers, and students about quality education practices in government elementary schools working in the province of Punjab. The post-HOC analysis through the least significant difference (LSD) among the views of headteachers, teachers, and students about quality education practices is given in the following table.

Table 3

Post-Hoc Analysis through LSD about QEP

Dependent variable	Respondents status	Respondents status	Mean difference	Std. Error	Sig. (p-value)
QEP	Headteachers	Students	22.58	.80854	.000
	Teacher	headteachers	13.50	.83455	.000
		Students	36.08	.32377	.000

$p < 0.05$

Table 3 depicts the post-hoc analysis through LSD (least significant difference test) about quality education practices in public elementary schools of Punjab. There was a significant difference among the views of teachers, headteachers and students about quality education practices in public elementary schools of Punjab at p value = 0.000, 0.000, and $0.000 < 0.05$, respectively. The positive mean differences of 22.58 and 13.50, 36.08 indicate that teachers reported better quality education practices than headteachers and students.

Table 4

Levels of Social-Emotional Learning

Variable	Status of Respondents	Levels						Mean score
		Low		Average		High		
		%	F	%	F	%	f	
Overall Social-Emotional Learning	Headteachers	01%	02/200	19.5%	39/200	79.5%	159/200	2.76
	Teachers	0%	0/1688	31%	524/1688	69%	1164/1688	2.69
	Students	0%	0/4011	05%	217/4011	95%	3783/4011	2.95

Criteria for establishing level by range.

Table 4 reflects the levels of Social-Emotional Learning of students. The 79.5% of headteachers (159/200) with a mean score = 2.76 reported a high level of overall social-emotional learning of students. The 69% of teachers (1164/1688) with mean score = 2.69 reported a high level of students' overall social-emotional learning. The 95% of students (3783/4011) with mean score = 2.95 reported a high level of overall social-emotional learning of students.

Table 5

Comparison of Headteachers' Teachers' and Students' Views of SEL

Dependent variables		Some of the squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig. (p-value)
Social Emotional Learning	Between Groups	45704.687	2	22852.344	97.523	.000
	Within Groups	1379022.500	5885	234.328		
	Total	1424727.18	5887			

$P < 0.05$

Table 5 reflects the comparison of views of headteachers, teachers, and students from public elementary schools in Punjab about the social-emotional learning of students. The F value 97.523 and p-value = 0.000 < 0.05 reveal the difference among the views of headteachers, teachers, and students about social-emotional learning of students studying in public elementary schools of Punjab was significant. The post-HOC analysis through the LSD (least significant difference) is given in the following table.

Table 6

Post-Hoc Analysis through LSD about SEL of Students

Variable	Respondents status	Respondents status	Mean difference	Std. Error	Sig. (p-value)
Social Emotional Learning	Teacher	Headteacher	10.64	1.14475	.000
	Student	Headteacher	13.96	1.10915	.000
		Teacher	3.32	.44430	.000

P<0.05

Table 6 depicts the post-hoc analysis through the LSD test about the Social-Emotional learning of students studying in government elementary schools of Punjab. The positive mean difference of 13.96 and 3.32 indicate that students reported better social-emotional learning than headteachers and teachers.

Table 7

Correlation between QEP and SEL (Headteachers' Responses)

Variables	r	Sig. 2-tailed (p-value)
Quality Education Social Emotional Learning	0.710	0.000

* (r) Pearson Correlation

Table 7 indicates a strong positive correlation between Quality Education Practices and Social-Emotional learning as indicated by $r = 0.710 > 0.01$, $p=0.00 < 0.005$ & $N= 200$.

Table 8

ANOVA (How will the regression equation fit the data)

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig. (p-value)
1	Regression	29390.001	1	29390.001	201.590	.000
	Residual	28866.594	198	145.791		
	Total	58256.595	199			

- a. Dependent Variable. Social Emotional Learning
- b. Predictors: (Constant). Quality Education Practices

Table 8 shows the regression model predicts the Quality of Education Practices in the Social-Emotional Learning of students studying in government elementary schools of Punjab. The F-value = 209.590 and the p-value = 0.00 < 0.05 shows that overall, the regression model statistically predicts the Social-Emotional Learning of students.

Table 9

Linear Regression Analysis among QEP and SEL (Headteachers' Responses)

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Std. Errors estimates
1	.710	.504	.502	12.07439

- a. Predictors: (Constant). process
- b. Dependent Variable. Social Emotional Learning

Table 9 shows the linear regression among Quality Education Practices and Social Emotional Learning of students of public elementary schools in Punjab. The R-value 0.710 represents the strong degree of correlation between Quality Education Practices and Social Emotional Learning of students of public elementary schools in Punjab. The R2 value = 0.504 indicates the output was the moderate predictor of Social Emotional Learning of students studying in government elementary schools in Punjab.

Table 10

Relationship between QEP and SEL (Teachers' Responses)

Variables	r	Sig. 2-tailed (p-value)
Quality Education Practices Social Emotional Learning	.757	0.000

*(r) Pearson correlation

Table 10 indicates that there was a strong positive correlation between (QEP) "Quality Education Practices" and (SEL) Social-Emotional learning of students as indicated by $r = 0.757$, $N=1688$, $p=0.00 < 0.001$.

Table 11

ANOVA (How will the regression equation fit the data)

Model		Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig. (p-value)
1	Regression	376386.160	1	376386.160	2258.614	.000 ^b
	Residual	280963.057	1686	166.645		
	Total	657349.217	1687			

- a. Dependent Variable. Social Emotional Learning
- b. Predictors: (Constant). Quality Education Practices

Table 11 shows the regression model predicts the Quality of Education Practices in students' Social-Emotional learning at public elementary schools in Punjab. The F- F-value = 2258.614 and the p-value $0.00 < 0.05$ shows that the regression model significantly predicts the Social Emotional Learning of students.

Table 12

Linear regression analysis among QEP and SEL (Teachers' Responses)

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Std. Errors estimates
1	.757 ^a	.573	.572	12.90910

- a. Predictors: (Constant). Quality Education Practices
- b. Dependent Variable. Social Emotional Learning

Table 12 shows the linear regression among Quality Education Practices and Social Emotional Learning of students of public elementary schools in Punjab. The R-value 0.757 represents the strong degree of correlation between Quality Education Practices and Social Emotional Learning of students of public elementary schools in Punjab. The R2 value = 0.573 indicates that Quality Education Practices were the moderate predictor of Social Emotional Learning of students of public elementary schools in Punjab.

Table 13

Relationship between QEP and SEL (Students' Responses)

Variables	r	Sig. 2-tailed (p-value)
Quality Education Practices Social Emotional Learning	.716	0.000

*(r) Pearson correlation

Table 13 shows a strong positive relationship between (QEP) “quality education practices” and (SEL) as reflected by $r = 0.716$, $N=1688$, $p=0.00 < 0.001$.

Table 14

ANOVA (How will the regression equation fit the data)

Model		Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F	Sig. (p-value)
1	Regression	339828.067	1	339828.067	4198.641	.000 ^b
	Residual	323588.621	3998	80.938		
	Total	663416.688	3999			

- c. Dependent Variable. Social Emotional Learning
- d. Predictors: (Constant). Quality Education Practices

Table 14 shows that the regression model indicates that the Quality of Education Practices predicts the students’ Social-Emotional Learning at public elementary schools in Punjab as indicated by F-value = 4198.641 and the p-value $0.000 < 0.05$. Overall, the regression model significantly predicts the Social Emotional Learning of students.

Table 15

Linear Regression Analysis among QEP and SEL (Students’ Responses)

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Std. Errors estimates
1	.716 ^a	.512	.512	8.99653

- c. Predictors: (Constant). Quality Education Practices
- d. Dependent Variable. Social Emotional Learning

Table 15 shows the linear regression among Quality Education Practices and Social Emotional Learning of students of public elementary schools in Punjab. The R-value 0.716 represents the strong degree of correlation between Quality Education Practices and Social Emotional Learning of students of public elementary schools in Punjab. The R² value = 0.512 indicates that Quality Education Practices were the moderate predictor of Social Emotional Learning of students of public elementary schools in Punjab.

Discussion

The major results were that most of the public elementary schools of Punjab had a high level of quality education practices, which is in line with the findings of the study of Javed, Ishaq, and Javed (2021). They found that most facilities were available in public elementary schools and were useable; the building and condition of schools’ buildings were acceptable; moreover, the student-teacher ratio and academic achievement of students were suitable. This finding is also like the findings of the study of Hussain, Ahmad, and Altaf (2023). They found that public schools had a good quality of management, monitoring, quality of teaching staff, assessment of students, and school arrangement, and schools followed the standards of quality of Education. Awan and Abdul (2020) also found that public schools in Punjab had suitable teaching staff, basic facilities, and infrastructure. The results of this study were also according to the initiatives and reforms taken by the Punjab Government to boost the quality of education and to address the challenges and were also according to the Punjab Education Sector Program (2019-2020, 2023-2024) launched by Punjab Government and proposed special attention on three areas of quality of education i.e. quality and learning outcomes, access and retention, equity and management (Govt. of Punjab, 2019).

Another conclusion was that most of the students of public sector elementary schools in Punjab had high level of Social-Emotional learning of students. This finding is similar to the findings of the study of Rehman, Shah, and

Malik (2023). They found that the majority of secondary-level students showed interpersonal relationships, communication skills, cooperation, decision-making, critical thinking skills and empathy at a moderate level. A study by Loeb, Christian, Hough, Meyer, Rice, and West (2018) also sported the conclusion that schools contribute to the students' Social-Emotional learning. Other findings were that QEP and SEL had a strong positive relationship, and QEP strongly predicted the SEL. These findings are like the results of the study of Shahid, Saleem, and Farooqi (2023), who conducted a study in secondary schools in Punjab and found that school climate had a positive relationship with knowledge about others, students' socialization, managing relations, awareness of themselves, and ability to plan. In another study, Hough, Kalogrides, and Loeb (2017) explored a positive relationship between school culture climate and the SEL.

The quality education practices and social-emotional learning of 8th-class students in public elementary schools were analyzed by comparison of headteachers' and teachers' views to cross-verify the results of the current study; however, no such contradiction was found in the collective views of headteachers, teachers, and students regarding QEP and SEL in public elementary schools of Punjab that validate the results of the current study. However, no other studies were available in this regard, and the possible reason is that other studies focus on gender, locality, and area-based comparison.

Conclusion

Most of the public elementary schools of Punjab had high levels of overall quality education practices, as reported by headteachers, teachers, and students. Overall, QEPs were far better in the views of headteachers than students' views, while in the views of teachers overall, QEPs were far better than headteachers and students. Most of the public elementary schools of Punjab had high levels of overall social-emotional learning of 8th-class students, as reported by headteachers, teachers, and students. Teachers reported better overall SEL of 8th-class students as compared to headteachers, while students reported better overall SEL of 8th-class students as compared to headteachers and teachers. The overall quality education practices had a strong positive relationship with overall social-emotional learning of 8th-class students in public sector elementary schools of Punjab, as collectively reported by headteachers, teachers, and students. It was concluded that overall quality education practices strongly predict the social-emotional learning of 8th-class students in public elementary schools of Punjab.

Recommendations

1. As Social-Emotional Learning (SEL) is the modern emerging trend in education since last decade and a lot of work has been done in it, especially CASEL therefore, it is recommended that policy policymakers, curriculum developers, and Textbook writers introduce reforms in curriculum and adopt a social-emotional learning model to get better effects of quality education practices on social-emotional learning of students.
2. It is also recommended that the Directorate of Staff Development of Punjab province of Pakistan introduce training programs for teachers to comprehend Social-Emotional Learning and improve the students' Social-Emotional Learning.

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